

Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine

[Analytics](#) | May 22, 2026

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- The applied research grants, EPC-20-007 and EPC-23-024, fund the development of the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine which transforms the foundational climate and environmental data that underpins California’s Climate Change Assessment into actionable information to improve electricity sector resilience. This platform provides users with customized data, advanced analytics, and powerful cloud computing resources, allowing users to perform high-level analysis without needing to download massive localized climate datasets. Enhanced metrics that convert climate data into electricity sector specific formulations and novel analytics direct users to the most relevant scenarios for their specific applications. The cloud-based data platform provides unprecedented computational resources to users, pre-loaded with easy-to-access capacity for the transformation of climate data into stakeholder identified formats, with supporting analytics guiding users to best practices and solutions for their specific application. Continual outreach provides foundational educational training and support to users of the data platform.

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Analytics

Analytics Overview

The Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine is designed to provide access and tools to utilize the rich set of climate data downscaled for California. The methodology for the prioritization of these tools is showcased in our section “Co-Production Process,” and is focused on gauging actual users’ needs of the data and incrementally developing working analytics tools in concert with users.

These tools are open source; we welcome feedback, suggestions, and requests for improvements, future features, and bug fixes in the applications produced. Guidelines for user contributions are available in the [climakitae documentation](#).

Our team’s mission for this project is to support informed decision making for California, inclusive of the best available climate science, on a variety of energy sector topics.

The resources below detail the tools produced and under development.

Methods

Methodologies for defining, generating, and utilizing climate datasets in the Analytics Engine, including Global Warming Levels and Climate Profiles.

Applications

Analytics Engine notebooks and their applications in climate data analysis and decision-making, including Notebooks & Development and Example Use Cases.

Training Resources

Detailed documentation of toolkits developed for working with climate data on the Analytics Engine and external resources for JupyterHub and other technical tools used on the platform.

Methods

This section provides an overview of the key methodologies used in the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine. Each page summarizes how specific datasets are defined, generated, and applied in climate analysis and decision-making.

Global Warming Levels

Describes the methods used to identify and use global warming level (GWL) datasets within the Analytics Engine, including how warming thresholds are defined, how simulations are grouped, and how users can apply GWL data in their analyses.

Climate Profiles

Outlines the methodologies behind climate profile datasets, including what they represent, how they are constructed, and how to interpret and apply them. This includes documentation for typical meteorological years (TMYs), standard year (SY), and related profile-generation approaches.

Extreme Value Analysis

Explains the statistical methods used for extreme value analysis in the Analytics Engine, including the Block Maxima/Minima Series approach, distribution fitting, return period and return value calculations, confidence interval estimation, and guidance on spatial, temporal, and simulation aggregation.

Global Warming Levels

Fetching Global Warming Level data in the Analytics Engine

This section outlines the steps a user takes to access data on global warming levels using *climakitae*. The tools in the AE platform can calculate global warming levels for dynamically downscaled (WRF) or statistically downscaled (LOCA) data using the same methods. For more information on how to select a dataset for an application of interest, refer to the Guidance section on the AE website titled [Using Climate Data in Decision-Making](#).

The specific methodology and calculations underlying the generation of GWL data are covered in the next section.

California climate data on GWLs can be retrieved in two ways depending on the user's preferred workflow:

1. Use the `get_data()` function in `climakitae`
2. Use a GUI that visually shows all available options
3. Use the `ClimateData` class in `climakitae`

Option 1: Retrieve WLS directly using the `get_data()` function

This method uses a simple function from the `data_interface` module in `climakitae` to retrieve warming levels data directly using a python function – no GUI required. This might be a good approach for a user that already knows what data they want, and doesn't need to examine the full set of options. More information and additional options are available in the `get_data()` function – this is accessible in the [basic_data_access.ipynb](#) notebook.

Some basic information on how to use this method is shown below. Users are encouraged to work through the notebook `climakitae_direct_data_download.ipynb` in the Analytics Engine for more details on how this function works.

1. Import the function from the `data_interface` module:

```
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_data
```

2. Optional: Print the function docstrings to see the possible function inputs. Note that some of these arguments require an input (variable, downscaling_method, resolution, and timescale), and some of the arguments are ignored for a warming level approach (time_slice and scenario).

```
print(get_data.__doc__)
```

3. Set the arguments to retrieve warming levels data:

```
get_data(  
    variable = "Precipitation (total)",  
    downscaling_method = "Dynamical",  
    resolution = "45 km",  
    timescale = "monthly",  
    approach = "Warming Level",  
    warming_level_window = 10,  
    warming_level = [2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0]  
)
```

Make sure the argument `approach` is set to `"Warming Level"`; the function defaults to a time-based approach. The argument `warming_level_window` defaults to 15 (years on either side, i.e. a 30 year window), and the argument `warming_level` defaults to `2.0` (2 deg C).

This method of grabbing GWL data can also be found in the [warming_level_methods.ipynb](#) notebook.

Option 2: Retrieving WLS through the GUI

To visualize the available data options and minimize the amount of coding, a GUI-based approach is also provided. To display the selections GUI in a notebook, run the following lines of code (which are also listed in the `getting_started.ipynb`):

```
import climakitae as ck
import climakitaegui as ckg
selections = ckg.Select()
selections.show()
```

After the last line is executed, the following panel pops up:

Data Options in the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine

Data Type:
 Gridded

Approach:
 Time
 Warming Level

Downscaling Method:
 Dynamical
 Statistical
 Dynamical+Statistical

Variable Type:
 Variable
 Station

Maximum air temperature at 2m

The maximum air temperature at 2m above the Earth's surface.

Variable Units:
 K
 degC
 degF

Timescale:
 daily
 monthly
 hourly

Model Grid-Spacing:
 3 km
 9 km
 45 km

WARMING LEVELS APPROACH: Options only valid if retrieval method is set to "Warming Level"

Years around Global Warming Level (+/-): e.g. 15 means a 30yr window
 1.5 2.0 2.5 3.0 4.0

15

TIME-BASED APPROACH: Options only valid if retrieval method is set to "Time"

Years: How do you want to time-slice the data?
 1980 .. 2015

Historical Data:
 Estimates of recent historical climatic conditions
 n/a

Future Model Data:
 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) represent different global emissions scenarios
 n/a

Location Options for the Selected Data

Weather station:
 Set data type to 'Station' to see options

Subset the data by...
 CA counties

Location selection
 Alameda County
 Alpine County
 Amador County
 Butte County

Latitude: 32.50 .. 42

Longitude: -125.50 .. -114

Compute an area average across grid cells within your selected region?
 Yes No

The two important sections that need to be defined before retrieving WL data are boxed in red. Similarly to the manual parameter definition above, the "Approach" must first be set to "Warming Level", then the desired time window ("Years around GWL") and desired warming levels can be selected (1.5 deg C - 4.0 deg C).

After making these selections, running `data = selections.retrieve()` in a following cell will load a warming levels data object. Below will show how this data is shaped and how to interact with it.

Working with the WL data object

The warming levels object will look like the following:

```
xarray.DataArray 'Maximum air temperature at
2m' (warming_level: 2, time_delta: 360, y: 8, x: 10, simulation: 10)
```

	Array	Chunk
Bytes	2.20 MiB	27.19 kiB
Shape	(2, 360, 8, 10, 10)	(1, 87, 8, 10, 1)
Count	184 Graph Layers	180 Chunks
Type	float32	numpy.ndarray

▼ Coordinates:

Coordinate	Value	Unit	Range
warming_level	(warming_level)	float64	2.0 2.5
time_delta	(time_delta)	float64	-180.0 -179.0 ... 178.0 179.0
x	(x)	float64	-4.035e+06 ... -3.954e+06
y	(y)	float64	1.484e+06 1.493e+06 ... 1.547e+06
lakemask	(y, x)	float32	0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 ... 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
landmask	(y, x)	float32	1.0 1.0 1.0 1.0 ... 1.0 1.0 1.0 1.0
lat	(y, x)	float32	39.23 39.28 39.33 ... 40.09 40.14
lon	(y, x)	float32	-121.7 -121.7 ... -121.5 -121.4
Lambert_Confo...	()	int64	0
centered_year	(warming_level, simulation)	int64	2039 2043 2035 ... 2069 2060 2049
simulation	(simulation)	<U44	'WRF_CESM2_r11i1p1f1_historical+...

► Attributes: (12)

The dimensions can be interpreted as follows:

- **warming_level:** the number of warming levels in the data object. Since we listed 2.0 and 2.5 warming levels in the examples above, we see that both 2.0 and 2.5 warming levels were retrieved in the resulting data object.
- **time_delta:** this is the number of time steps from the center warming level year in this object. Since we specified monthly data with a 30-year window, this results in 360 time steps (30 years x 12 months). The time steps are labeled with coordinate values of -180 to 179, with a time_delta= 0 indicating the year that the climate simulation reaches the specified global warming level.
- **y, x:** spatial dimensions for WRF data
- **simulation:** the simulation names grabbed for this set of parameters, where the names are listed as: [Downscaling_Method]_[Model]_[Ensemble Member]_[Historical Data Used]_[SSP]

There may be warnings that pop up when using warming level data that look like the following:

WARNING FOR WARMING LEVELS APPROACH

There may be NaNs in your data for certain simulation/warming level combinations if the warming level is not reached for that particular simulation before the year 2100.

This does not mean you have missing data, but rather a feature of how the data is combined in retrieval to return a single data object.

If you want to remove these empty simulations, it is recommended to first subset the data object by each individual warming level and then dropping NaN values.

These are only printed to illustrate the limitations of the data object returned, as different warming levels may have a different number of simulations that reach that given warming level.

Option 3: Retrieve WLS directly using the ClimateData class

This is a new method for loading data through *climakitae*. This approach offers more flexibility and faster performance, but is still actively in development and may undergo changes. Some basic information on the data loading operation with the ClimateData object is below, but users are encouraged to work through the `warming_level_methods.ipynb` notebook in the Analytics Engine for more details.

1. Create a ClimateData object called `cd`, which will be used to grab GWL data:

```
from climakitae.new_core.user_interface import ClimateData
cd = ClimateData()
```

2. Set the arguments to retrieve warming levels data:

```
tasmax_gwl_data = (cd
    .catalog("cadcat")
    .activity_id("LOCA2")
    .table_id("mon")
    .grid_label("d03")
    .variable("tasmax")
    .processes({
        "warming_level": {
            "warming_levels": [0.8, 2.0],
            "warming_level_window": 15,
        },
    })
    .get()
)
```


The above example is loading data at two specific warming levels (0.8 and 2.0) with a 15-year window for the Max Temp.

An SSP was not specified to load the data because simulations from any SSP can be used to measure climate impacts at a given GWL. This ability to utilize data from all SSPs equivalently is one of the benefits of the GWL approach.

How California-focused Warming Level data is Calculated

This section outlines the methodology for calculating data on GWL in the Analytics Engine. These are the calculations that are implemented in *climakitae* and are used when retrieving GWL data as described in the previous section. The methods described here follow the approach used by the [IPCC AR6 report](#) as closely as possible.

Note: The lookup tables described here are used for selecting data from each model, but are not an accurate way to estimate what year a GWL is most likely to be reached. To estimate the timing of GWLs, the Analytics Engine uses the IPCC's warming trajectories, as described on the [About the Data](#) page. Detailed information on how timing estimates for global warming levels are calculated and how to translate a specific target year into a GWL (and vice versa) can be found in the [warming_level_timing_explorer.ipynb](#) notebook on the Analytics Engine.

Calculating GWL on the Analytics Engine is a two-step process:

1. Generate the GWL lookup Tables for Models

For each global climate model (GCM) simulation in the CMIP6 archive, the average global temperature increase relative to pre-industrial conditions (1850-1900) is measured for each year. This time-series of global warming is smoothed with a 20-year running average and used to create a lookup table to determine when each simulation reaches a given global warming level.

2. Retrieve the Analytics Engine Model data at selected GWL years

Using the years that each global simulation reaches a specified warming level as determined by the GWL lookup table in step 1, the corresponding years of data are taken from each regionally downscaled climate simulation. A slice of the time series (typically 30 years) is taken from each simulation, centered on the year that simulation reaches the specified warming level. This data therefore represents the estimated regional climate impacts that will be felt at a given level of global warming.

A detailed description of how these two steps are implemented in the Analytics Engine is described below:

Step 1: Generate the GWL lookup tables for models

The GWL lookup table captures what year each global climate simulation reaches each warming level. This table is pre-generated in the *climakitae* repository, and is only updated if changes are made to the methodology or new warming levels are added to the platform. No actions are required by the user for this step, but the section is provided as technical documentation and outlines the method used to generate this table for transparency.

1. From the [CMIP6 catalog](#), all CMIP6 models and their ensemble members are selected via the Pangeo CMIP6 [CSV](#).
2. Global average surface air temperature for each ensemble member is then calculated by a spatially weighted average of the `tas` (or appropriate surface air temperature) variable using this formula (which is essentially a weighted average of all grid cells around the world, which accounts for the fact that grid cells towards the poles are smaller than grid cells near the equator):

```
weightlat = np.sqrt(np.cos(np.deg2rad(ensemble_mem[lat])))
weightlat = weightlat / np.sum(weightlat)
timeseries = (ensemble_mem * weightlat).sum(lat).mean(lon)
```

3. Each time series is smoothed with a 20-year running average window. Then, the month/year that each time-series first exceeds a certain degree of warming (1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0) relative to the average temperature from a given reference period is computed and then saved per model into a lookup table of GWL, with the model as the index.
4. The lookup tables are saved in the data directory of the *climakitae* repository:
 - a. `gwl_1850-1900ref.csv` uses the reference period 1850-1900, consistent with the IPCC warming level definitions. This reference period can not be used to calculate anomalies (different from historical), because the downscaled data only extends back to 1950.
 - b. `gwl_1980-2010ref.csv` uses the reference period 1980-2010, and is only used when calculating anomalies.
 - c. A 20-year running average window is used to determine the “crossing year” for each GWL by the center of the window. This ensures that any one particularly high value year does not skew the results when the overall average temperature trend has not yet reached the warming level.
5. Additionally, the GWL at each month is saved for each ensemble member from 1860-2090 into `gwl_1850-1900ref_timeidx.csv` and `gwl_1980-2010ref_timeidx.csv`. These act as translations between time and WLS.
 - a. These files have time as the index, whereas the files generated in Step 3 have the model as the index.
 - b. The time range of these files is 1860-2090 because the 20-year running average window clips the first and last 10 years.
6. The above steps are calculated for all CMIP6 models. The CESM2-LENS data is processed separately due to a slightly different data structure, but follows the same methodology.

Example of GWL lookup tables

WL-based indexing (Step 1, part 3): [gwl_1850-1900ref.csv](#)

	GCM	run	scenario	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
1	ACCESS-CM2	r3i1p1f1	ssp585	2037-07-16 12:00:00	2046-05-16 12:00:00	2053-11-16 00:00:00	2060-10-16 12:00:00
2	ACCESS-CM2	r3i1p1f1	ssp370	2039-05-16 12:00:00	2048-12-16 12:00:00	2058-10-16 12:00:00	2068-06-16 00:00:00
3	ACCESS-CM2	r3i1p1f1	ssp245	2040-05-16 12:00:00	2051-01-16 12:00:00	2066-02-15 00:00:00	2082-04-16 00:00:00
4	ACCESS-CM2	r4i1p1f1	ssp585	2033-06-16 00:00:00	2044-01-16 12:00:00	2051-09-16 00:00:00	2058-09-16 00:00:00
5	ACCESS-CM2	r4i1p1f1	ssp370	2035-04-16 00:00:00	2045-06-16 00:00:00	2054-10-16 12:00:00	2062-11-16 00:00:00
6	ACCESS-CM2	r4i1p1f1	ssp245	2036-12-16 12:00:00	2048-09-16 00:00:00	2062-06-16 00:00:00	2079-05-16 12:00:00
7	ACCESS-CM2	r5i1p1f1	ssp585	2033-03-16 12:00:00	2042-02-15 00:00:00	2050-05-16 12:00:00	2057-08-16 12:00:00
8	ACCESS-CM2	r5i1p1f1	ssp370	2034-05-16 12:00:00	2044-02-15 12:00:00	2054-03-16 12:00:00	2064-03-16 12:00:00
9	ACCESS-CM2	r5i1p1f1	ssp245	2036-01-16 12:00:00	2048-01-16 12:00:00	2059-11-16 00:00:00	2074-06-16 00:00:00
10	ACCESS-CM2	r1i1p1f1	ssp585	2034-02-15 00:00:00	2044-01-16 12:00:00	2051-11-16 00:00:00	2059-06-16 00:00:00

Time-based indexing (Step 1, part 4): [gwl_1850-1900ref_timeidx.csv](#)

	time	ACCESS-CM2_r3i1p1f1_ssp585	ACCESS-CM2_r3i1p1f1_ssp370	ACCESS-CM2_r3i1p1f1_ssp245	ACCESS-CM2_r2i1p1f1_ssp585
2	1860-1	0.021848000429216797	0.021848000429216797	0.021848000429216797	0.07927943564445693
3	1860-10	0.024807404680983563	0.024807404680983563	0.024807404680983563	0.08083179408401264
4	1860-11	0.024693259768447953	0.024693259768447953	0.024693259768447953	0.08040738546074616
5	1860-12	0.02545233323090912	0.02545233323090912	0.02545233323090912	0.08039919768228596
6	1860-2	0.02320383171376316	0.02320383171376316	0.02320383171376316	0.08005929805050158
7	1860-3	0.024557924282568422	0.024557924282568422	0.024557924282568422	0.08049298298975387
8	1860-4	0.02599134114518904	0.02599134114518904	0.02599134114518904	0.08205755893113557
9	1860-5	0.025747648063607423	0.025747648063607423	0.025747648063607423	0.08265583439719607
10	1860-6	0.026179440133764588	0.026179440133764588	0.026179440133764588	0.08311309125218548
11	1860-7	0.026149973301914525	0.026149973301914525	0.026149973301914525	0.08368777878058727
12	1860-8	0.02542210063184906	0.02542210063184906	0.02542210063184906	0.08262678312070548
13	1860-9	0.02499533212023337	0.02499533212023337	0.02499533212023337	0.08214614455590805
14	1861-1	0.026746247678208827	0.026746247678208827	0.026746247678208827	0.08087332043132728
15	1861-10	0.026218216555667577	0.026218216555667577	0.026218216555667577	0.08052708391801697

Step 2: Retrieval of the Analytics Engine model data at selected GWLs

When data on warming levels is retrieved using `get_data()` or the Select GUI, the following procedure will be run:

For each warming level:

For each simulation within our AE WRF/LOCA2-Hybrid catalog (depending on downscaling method):

- A. Find the centered year that that simulations passes this global warming level using the table generated from step 3 in Global Warming Level calculations ([gwl_1850-1900ref.csv](#))

Climate Profiles

Overview

Many energy system modeling and other planning processes are designed to intake hourly information to capture short term fluctuations in conditions that affect power supply and demand ([NYSERDA 2020](#); [Smith et al. 2025](#)). An annualized hourly climate profile is a dataset that contains hourly weather conditions at a given location for an entire year. Because it represents every hour of a 1-year period, a climate profile is also commonly referred to as an “8760” (the number of hours in one year). Although climate profiles have previously been generated using historical observation-based datasets, planners are increasingly interested in using annualized climate profiles that are constructed with future climate data. Annualized hourly climate profiles are able to represent future weather conditions due to a changing climate and can thus better inform design and planning processes for a wide range of future needs.

There are multiple kinds of climate profiles, including:

- *Synthetically* generated climate profiles, in which the climate profile is not selected from a single continuous model year; rather, each component (e.g., hour or month) is selected across the statistical distribution and then concatenated together to build a full year profile.
- *Actual or realistic* climate profiles, in which a single continuous year of either historical or future weather conditions is used as a representative of annual hourly conditions.

The Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine currently provides two kinds of synthetic climate profiles:

1. **Standard Year 8760:** One year of hourly data that represents any desired statistical percentile of weather conditions for a location over a 30-year climatological period. A Standard Year builds a climate profile for each climate model on a single variable and can be used to evaluate either median or extreme conditions by selecting appropriate percentiles. Both historical and future Standard Year 8760s are available.
2. **Typical Meteorological Year 8760 (TMY):** One year of hourly data that represents the median weather conditions for a location over a climatological period. A TMY file is built from ten specific weather variables that are weighted in compliance with international standards ([Wilcox and Marion 2008](#)). TMY files statistically assess the median conditions from 30 years of model data and select the most “typical” month for each month during a year. The resulting TMY file includes multiple variables and has very specific formatting requirements. Both historical and future TMY (FTMY) 8760s are available.

Coming onto the Analytics Engine in 2026!

3. **Extreme 8760s:** One year of hourly data that represents extreme weather conditions for a location over a climatological period. These profiles will include extreme TMYs (XMY), Stress Test 8760s, and other kinds of extreme climate profiles.

Accessing the Data

Climate Profiles are accessible on the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine in two locations:

1. An extensive set of pre-generated Standard Years and FTMYS are available in the [Cal-Adapt: Data Catalog](#). The pre-generated Standard Year 8760s and FTMYS are available for four common energy sector planning horizons: present-day (1.2°C GWL), near-future (1.5°C GWL), mid-century (2.0°C GWL), and mid-late-century (2.5°C). For more information on global warming levels (GWL), see our guidance here.
2. To generate a custom climate profile, including a custom GWL-based or time-based FTMYS, check out the [custom climate profiles notebook](#), available on the Analytics Engine JupyterHub. Standard Year 8760s are not available via a time-based approach.

Standard Year 8760s

Methodology

A Standard Year is one year of hourly data that represents a statistical percentile of meteorological conditions for a location over a set amount of time (30 years). For example, for each hour of the year, the 90th percentile is taken across the same hour of the year from each of the 30 years of data. A Standard Year can be generated for any climate variable (temperature, solar radiation, etc.), any desired percentile (median and extremes), and for any location of interest. On AE, Standard Years can be generated for **gridded areas** and **point locations** across WECC. The Standard Year profile is built by selecting the real simulation value closest to the selected percentile for each hour of the year. The Standard Year profile is a synthetic profile, and thus differs from using a single continuous year of climate model data. Functionality to generate a “delta Standard Year” is also provided, in which a difference between the timeframe of interest and the historical reference period is returned. This can be used to evaluate climate change impacts on energy systems over time (see our guidance on Reference Periods).

Step 1: User selects desired information.

A user will first select four primary settings, with additional options:

1. The variable of interest to build the Standard Year. A user can optionally select alternative units, if so desired.
2. The percentile of interest, at which the variable is evaluated against the statistical distribution. The default percentile is the 50th percentile.
3. The location of interest, including both gridded areas (e.g., county, service territory) and point-locations (e.g., weather station, utility asset).
4. The timeframe of interest. On AE, Standard Years are currently calculated using global warming levels. A user can generate a Standard Year with any desired warming level, including custom levels (e.g., 1.37°C). A user can also optionally elect to calculate a delta Standard Year or an absolute Standard Year. An absolute Standard Year represents the values at the designated warming level, while a delta Standard Year calculates the difference between the selected warming level and a 1.2°C historical reference warming level.

Step 2: Compute distribution and select candidate hour for each hour.

At this stage, the data corresponding to the user selections (Step 1) are retrieved, and the statistical distribution is computed. The closest value from the distribution of simulation values at a given hour is then identified and returned for each hour of the year. This process is repeated for all 8 available dynamically-downscaled models on AE, including the 4 bias-adjusted models. The bias-adjusted and non-bias adjusted models are not collectively evaluated on the same distribution. Rather, the distribution is developed per model, and a separate profile for each model is returned. If a delta Standard Year is requested, the process is repeated for the selected warming level and the historical reference warming level (1.2°C) and the difference calculated for each model.

Step 3: Generate the Standard Year 8760 file.

Once each representative hour is selected, each model's climate profile information is compiled into a single Standard Year file, with clear designations for each model's profile. Standard Year files are provided in .csv format for ease of use. On the AE Jupyter Hub, an absolute Standard Year for a point location takes approximately 5 minutes to generate, and 20 minutes for a gridded area (based on LA County).

Note: a Standard Year can be generated for all of California, but it will take over an hour to complete.

Applications

After generating Standard Year files, users may ask what steps to take next. When generating Standard Year files on the AE, the AE intentionally returns a separate climate profile for each model, all contained within one Standard Year file. No further aggregation or downsampling is performed, as the appropriate approach depends on the user's specific application and need for the Standard Year information. The following guidance is provided to support next steps in using these data.

When to evaluate the range of results

The differences between profiles from each climate model represents a sample of uncertainty from model differences and the natural variability of the climate. Examining these differences can provide valuable information about the possible range of future climate conditions. When an application requires understanding a range of future climate impacts using climate profiles, it is recommended to generate profiles at multiple percentiles for comparison. From there, users should evaluate the differences between models to determine how they inform the analysis. At this stage, users may elect to aggregate the model climate profiles within the Standard Year file and conduct an uncertainty analysis across the results.

When to aggregate results

If an application requires a single climate profile, users may elect to aggregate results across climate models. It is recommended to first evaluate climate profiles from all of the available models to understand the spread of results and how that may affect the aggregated result.

- **Multi-model median:** Computing a multi-model median across all model climate profiles is recommended when the application is sensitive to outliers or extreme values within the model range.
- **Multi-model mean:** Computing a multi-model mean across all model climate profiles is recommended when the application is not sensitive to outliers or extreme values within the model range.
- **Multi-model range:** Consider calculating the multi-model difference for each hour between the “max” and “min” model spread of conditions as a measure of uncertainty in addition to the multi-model aggregation.

When to select a single model

If an aggregated Standard Year (e.g., multi-model median) is not appropriate or desired (e.g. when it is necessary to retain a single model’s synthetic record rather than aggregate), users may elect to pick a climate profile from a particular model. It is recommended to first evaluate all of the available models to understand where each falls in the spread of “median” conditions. Additionally, it is strongly recommended to document *which* model was selected and *why*.

- Based on whether the application is sensitive to outliers and extreme values, select either the median model (application is sensitive) or the most average model (application is not sensitive).
- If the range between models is very small, or not critical for the application or location, any model can serve as a representation of the ensemble.

When to weight results

Weighting may be appropriate when an application involves multiple locations in the analysis of Standard Year data. Weighting options can include:

- Population weighting – for building capacity, or in comparison across different locations
- Location-based weighting – if your area of interest falls between several different weather stations
- Load weighting – for generation and demand forecasting capacity across a service territory
- Building design weighting – for comparison amongst different building types (e.g., commercial vs. residential)
- Weighting amongst different variables for a given location (e.g., temperature, humidity)

Typical Meteorological Year 8760s

Methodology

A TMY profile is one year of hourly data that represents the median meteorological conditions for a point location over a set amount of time (at least 15 years required). AE recommends and utilizes a 30-year period for TMY calculation, which adheres to compliance with global warming level calculations. A TMY profile is built from ten specific weather variables that are weighted based on TMY standards ([NSRDB](#), [Wilcox and Marion 2008](#)). TMYs statistically assess the median conditions for those variables and select

the most “typical” month for each month during a year. These are compiled into a single climate profile. For example, the most “typical” January within the 30 year period could be from 2010, while the most “typical” February could be from 2022, and so on. The end result is an hourly climate profile for an entire year with each month spliced together from multiple input years. TMY profiles are widely used as critical inputs for energy modeling, simulating solar energy conversion systems, and evaluating building standards and energy efficiency ([NSRDB](#), [Wilcox and Marion 2008](#); [Laxo 2023](#)).

Note: The TMY method and weighting schema in the Analytics Engine mirrors the NREL TMY version 3 method ([NSRDB](#), [Wilcox and Marion 2008](#)).

Step 1: User selects location of interest and timeframe of interest (Historical TMY or Future TMY).

Calculating a historical or future TMY on AE is for point-based information, meaning that a user will first select a specific location of interest (e.g., a power plant or an airport weather station). At this point, the user will also select a period of time, such as a historical or future TMY (FTMY). On the AE, at least 15 years of daily data is required; the AE uses a default 30-year period. On AE, TMYs can be generated either via global warming level or time-based periods.

Step 2: Data is retrieved.

The input data for determining a “typical” month is retrieved for that location, which includes the following variables:

- Mean air temperature
- Min air temperature
- Max air temperature
- Mean dew point temperature
- Min dew point temperature
- Max dew point temperature
- Mean wind speed
- Max wind speed
- Global irradiance
- Direct irradiance

It is important to note that only the 4 bias-adjusted WRF downscaled models have all of the required variables to calculate a TMY profile – in particular, the two solar variables. The AE thus subsets the data to only include the relevant models. The last step in the data retrieval process is to ensure that all of the input data is in the **local time zone** for the location of interest. Because the input data is in UTC, the minimum temperature in hourly data “appears” on the day before (i.e., midnight on Monday in UTC corresponds to 5pm PST on Sunday). Converting to the local timezone is important to ensure that the daily minimum occurs on the correct day.

Step 3: Calculate the long-term climatological distribution.

The TMY method specifically uses a cumulative distribution function (CDF), which calculates the 30-year climatological distribution for each variable. This distribution is used as a baseline to determine which specific month within the 30-year period is closest to this baseline condition, and is repeated for all months (i.e., climatologically typical January, climatologically typical February, etc.).

Figure 1. An example of the long-term climatological conditions of daily max air temperature, for use in a TMY. This CDF represents the baseline conditions of January max air temperatures in 4 bias-adjusted WRF models at Los Angeles International Airport (LAX) from 1990-2020.

Step 4: Calculate the per-year per-month distribution.

The AE then calculates the CDF for each month of each year (i.e., January 2001, January 2002, and so on). This process is repeated for all variables. At this point the AE also removes specific months from consideration if they occurred during major volcanic eruptions like Pinatubo (June 1991 to December 1994), because volcanic aerosols have a major impact on solar variables.

Figure 2. An example of a candidate month's daily max air temperature, for use in a TMY. This CDF represents the January 2015 conditions of max air temperatures in 4 bias-adjusted WRF models at Los Angeles International Airport (LAX). The TMY process identifies the closest candidate month to the long-term climatological conditions to pick a "typical" month of January. For example, one would look for the closest instance of the distribution in this Figure to that of the first figure.

Step 5: Identify the month closest to climatology.

The long-term climatological distribution (Step 3) is then compared to the monthly distribution (Step 4) for each variable. The closest individual month to the climatology is determined by a [F-S statistic](#), which describes the absolute difference between the climatological distribution and each candidate month's distribution profile.

Step 6: Weight the input variables.

The results from the F-S statistic (Step 5) are then weighted based on the input variables. The AE uses the NREL scheme, which places higher weight on the solar variables due to their use in building and solar renewables applications:

- Mean air temperature: 2/20, or 10%
- Min air temperature: 1/20, or 5%
- Max air temperature: 1/20, or 5%
- Mean dew point temperature: 2/20, or 10%
- Min dew point temperature: 1/20, or 5%
- Max dew point temperature: 1/20, or 5%
- Mean wind speed: 1/20, or 5%
- Max wind speed: 1/20, or 5%
- Global irradiance: 5/20, or 25%

- Direct irradiance: 5/20, or 25%

Since the TMY methodology heavily weights the solar radiation input data, be aware that the final selection of “typical” months may not be typical for the non-solar radiation variables. In other words, what is selected as a typical June is based on the heavily weighted solar radiation conditions. That same month may not equally represent typical median June air temperatures.

Note: The [ISO method](#) for calculating TMYs utilizes a different weighting scheme, instead prioritizing air temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed.

Step 7: Select candidate month for each month of the year.

Once weighted, the AE selects the top month for each month of the year that has the lowest weighted sum, meaning that the candidate month is the closest or most “typical” to the long-term climatology for that specific month. The AE TMY method ensures that model data is kept intact, meaning that the most typical month is selected from the same model, not across models (e.g., not: January from MIROC6 and February from EC-Earth3). The end result of this process is that a TMY profile is generated for each model. This provides a great opportunity to be able to do multi-model comparisons of TMY profiles in a physically consistent space.

Step 8: Generate the TMY 8760 profile.

Once the “typical” months are selected, the AE generates the full hourly information by providing the standard meteorological information for a TMY profile. A TMY profile includes information on: air temperature, dewpoint temperature, relative humidity, global irradiance, direct irradiance, diffuse irradiance, downwelling radiation, wind speed and direction, and surface air pressure, for each of the specific months determined by Step 7 for all four models. [Smoothing](#) at the monthly interface between months is performed via curve fit to prevent discontinuities between months ([Wilcox and Marion 2008](#)). TMY profiles are provided in several formats, based on the user’s needs: .csv, [.epw](#), and [.tmy](#). On AE, a TMY profile for a point location takes approximately 40 minutes to generate.

Figure 3. An example historical TMY hourly profile for Los Angeles International Airport (LAX) for the 1990-2020 period, from MPI-ESM1-2-HR.

Applications

A TMY dataset is a specific kind of annualized hourly climate profile. They represent the most typical conditions for multiple variables during a designated climatological period and include the natural diurnal and seasonal variations that occur within a 1-year period (NSRDB). Because TMYs are specifically developed for long-term planning of solar energy and to inform the design of buildings, the variables and weights that they use are therefore also specific to these applications. It is critical to note that although TMYs may reduce simulation workload associated with evaluating every year of data for different

variables ([Qian et al. 2023](#)), misapplication of TMY data into planning processes can propagate misfitted assumptions about “median conditions” into risk assessments, infrastructure planning, and policy design.

Example appropriate applications of TMYs

- Average annual building energy consumption and design simulations ([Wilcox and Marion 2008](#); [NYSERDA 2020](#); [Sobie and Curry 2025](#)), especially heating and cooling loads
- Production estimates and performance comparisons of different energy systems types, especially solar systems ([Wilcox and Marion 2008](#); [Crawley and Lawrie 2015](#); [Chowdhury 2023](#); [Li et al. 2023](#); [Zeng et al. 2025](#))
- Energy asset and equipment sizing ([NYSERDA 2020](#))

Example inappropriate applications of TMY

- Extreme event analysis, including high-impact hazards such as extreme heat, cold spells, wildfire ([Wilcox and Marion 2008](#); [Peltier et al. 2024](#); [NYSERDA 2020](#)) and power outages ([NYSERDA 2020](#)) (see XMYs below for extreme event analysis)
- Capturing compounding and cascading events (see XMYs below for extreme event analysis)
- Historical TMYs should not be used for future building design ([Li et al. 2023](#); [Zeng et al. 2025](#); [Laxo 2023](#)) (see FTMYS below)
- Evaluation of actual system performance ([NYSERDA 2020](#))
- Near-real time forecasting ([Wilcox and Marion 2008](#))
- Custom weighting of variables; although alternative approaches may be appropriate based on specific use cases (e.g., specific building applications; [Qian et al. 2023](#))

Common Acronyms & Shorthand for TMYs

- **TMY: Typical Meteorological Year** - A TMY that provides the median conditions. TMYs can be computed for historical periods of time (a Historical TMY) or a future period of time (a Future TMY). The TMYs generated on AE are model-based TMYs.
- **Historical TMY** - A TMY profile that provides median weather conditions for a historical period, which can be derived from historical observations or historical climate model data.
- **FTMY: Future Typical Meteorological Year** - A TMY that provides median weather conditions for a future period, which can only be derived from future climate model data.
- **XMY: Extreme Typical Meteorological Year** - A TMY that provides extreme weather conditions, either for a historical or future period, which can only be derived from model data. XMYs may also be referred to as “EMY”.
- **AMY: Actual Meteorological Year** - The observed historical weather conditions from a specific year, which is used as a comparison to the synthetically-generated composite TMY year.

Note: AE has previously used “average meteorological year” for single-variable 8760s, which was also referred to as “AMY”. This terminology has been removed from the AE to avoid confusion.

Future TMYS

Future TMYS (FTMYS) incorporate future climate model data into a TMY framework using the same variables and weighting scheme. Given the multi-decadal lifespan of buildings and potential changes to energy system performance under climate conditions, FMTYs enable more forward-looking assessments of expected changes in their performance than TMYS constructed using historical data ([Laxo 2023](#); [NYSERDA 2020](#); [Chowdhury 2023](#); [Bass and New 2020](#); [Smith et al. 2025](#); [Sobie and Curry 2025](#); [Rady et al. 2025](#); [Peltier et al. 2024](#)).

Recommendations for FTMYS

- Carefully consider whether a global warming level or a time-based approach for calculating a FTMYS, especially with regards to projected climatic change over several decades ([Laxo 2023](#); [Sobie and Curry 2025](#)). On AE, FTMYS can be calculated using a [Global Warming Level](#) approach which ensures consistency between future climate projections and reduces uncertainties resulting from the wide range of climate sensitivity in climate models
- Select the location of interest as needed by the analysis, rather than relying on weather station locations.. Historical observation-based TMYS are historically based on weather station locations which may be far away from urban areas and not accurately reflect the actual highly localized microclimatic environment, especially for phenomena such as the urban heat island effect ([Li et al. 2023](#)). On AE, TMYS and FTMYS can be calculated at any location within the WECC area, given latitude and longitude coordinates.

Extreme TMYS

Extreme TMYS (XMYs) are fairly new extensions of TMYS, which has been enabled by the increasing use of climate model simulations to statistically assess and characterize extremes. There is currently no one recommended or accepted methodology for calculating an XMY. However, the general intent of an XMY is to select more extreme months (e.g., [Crawley and Lawrie 2015](#); [Crawley and Lawrie 2019](#); [Bass and New 2020](#); [Zeng et al. 2025](#)) instead of the median conditions represented in a TMY, and to use a large set of climate model simulations to do so. Energy sector practitioners are interested in XMYs and extreme 8760s in order to better understand how a changing climate will affect building performance and other similar applications. This will require guidance, updated standards, and trust in the data to do so ([Peltier et al. 2024](#)). AE intends to release extreme 8760s in 2026, alongside associated guidance and referenceable material.

Next steps: working with TMY files

After generating model-based TMY files, users may ask what steps to take next. When generating TMY files on the AE, one TMY file *per model* is returned. No further aggregation or downsampling is performed, as the appropriate approach depends on the user's specific application and need for the TMY information. The following guidance is provided to support next steps in using these data.

When to evaluate the range of results

When the application requires an understanding of the range of future, or even extreme, options using a TMY data format, it is first recommended to evaluate whether a TMY, FTM, or XMY is the most appropriate dataset to use. If a TMY or FTM is needed, it is **recommended to use a GWL-based TMY or FTM, instead of a time-based climatological reference period**. The GWL method reduces uncertainties between models and alleviates the [hot model problem](#), so that the user can more directly compare model-based FTMs at a specific planning horizon. From there, evaluate the differences between models and how they can inform the analysis. At this stage, users may elect to aggregate the FTMs and conduct an uncertainty analysis across the results.

When to aggregate results

If an application requires a single TMY, users may elect to aggregate results. It is recommended to evaluate TMs from all of the available models to understand where each falls in the spread of conditions as well as the need for physically consistent results.

- **Multi-model median:** A TMY itself is designed to capture median conditions, therefore calculating a multi-model median may be the most appropriate aggregation approach. A multi-model median is recommended over a multi-model mean, because the mean is sensitive to outliers (extreme values) whereas a median is not, even with a “typical” TMY. Different considerations should be made for XMs (forthcoming).
- **Multi-model range:** Consider calculating the multi-model difference for each hour between the “max” and “min” model spread of conditions as a measure of uncertainty in addition to the multi-model median.

When to select a single model

If an aggregated TMY (e.g., multi-model median) is not appropriate or desired (e.g. when it is necessary to retain a single model’s synthetic record rather than aggregate), users may elect to select a TMY from a single model. It is recommended that users first evaluate all of the available models to understand where each falls in the spread of “median” conditions. Additionally, it is strongly recommended that users document *which* model was selected and *why*.

- **Selecting the median model:** A TMY itself is designed to capture median conditions, therefore the median model may be the most appropriate selection.
- **Selecting any model:** If the range between models is very small, or not critical for the application or location, any model can serve as a representation of the ensemble.

When to weight results

Weighting may be appropriate for the user’s application if the user needs to consider multiple locations in their analysis using TMY data. For example, weighting TMY profiles for a gridded area assessment is a common application, especially in the Building Standards space. Weighting options may include:

- **Population weighting:** for building capacity, or in comparison across different locations

- **Location-based weighting:** if your area of interest falls between several different weather stations
- **Load weighting:** for generation and demand forecasting capacity across a service territory
- **Building design weighting:** for comparison amongst different building types (e.g., commercial vs. residential)

Extreme Value Analysis

Introduction

The [climakitae package](#) available on the Analytics Engine (AE) provides numerous tools to assist with [Extreme Value Analysis](#). This includes the calculation of [return probabilities](#), [return periods](#), and [return values](#). These terms are defined below within the context of meteorology and hydrology.

Return probability: The probability that a climate or weather event will exceed a specified magnitude in any given year ([Wilks 2011](#)).

- For example, if the maximum temperature at a location has a 10% chance of exceeding 105°F in any year, the annual **return probability** of that temperature is 0.10.

Return period: The reciprocal of the return probability. This is commonly interpreted as the average expected wait time between threshold exceedances ([Cooley 2011](#), [Douglas 2002](#), [Volpi 2015](#), [Wilks 2011](#)).

- If the return probability of exceeding 105°F is 0.10 per year, the **return period** of that event is $1 \div 0.10$ or 10 years.

Return value: The magnitude of a climate or weather event associated with a given return probability. Also called a return level ([Coles 2001](#), [Cooley 2011](#)).

- The 105°F threshold that has a 10% chance of being exceeded in a given year would be the 1-in-10 year **return value** for maximum temperature.

Extreme value analysis can be applied within the [Global Warming Levels](#) approach to compare return variables (return probability, period, or value) across warming levels ([Li 2021](#), [Slater 2021](#)). A time-based approach can also be used.

Methodology

Block Maxima/Minima Series

The threshold tools on AE have implemented the Block Maxima/Minima Series (BMS) method for the stationary, single-variable case. In this method, a time series is divided into a series of evenly sized blocks. The collection of maximum or minimum values from these blocks is called the BMS. A statistical distribution is fitted to the BMS and then used to obtain return probabilities, values, or periods ([Coles](#)

[2001](#), [Cooley 2011](#)). A typical block size for this method is one year, giving an [Annual Maxima/Minima Series \(AMS\)](#). The AMS or BMS can be obtained for data with any sub-annual time frequency including hourly, daily, and monthly frequencies. This method cannot be used to study extremes that are expected to occur more frequently than once per block.

Effective Sample Size

Meteorological data is often temporally autocorrelated, meaning that the value at a given time depends to some degree on the value(s) at past times. When the data within a block of the BMS has too much autocorrelation it can bias the result of the extreme value analysis. One way to manage temporal autocorrelation in the blocks is to compute the [effective sample size \(ESS\)](#) within each block and increase the block size as needed to obtain a sufficiently large ESS. The ESS is a scaled-down sample size that reflects the loss of information in a sample due to autocorrelation ([Zwiers and Von Storch, 1995](#)).

The *climakitae* package offers the option to check the effective sample size of blocks and generate a warning when the effective sample size is below a minimum threshold value (by default this threshold is 25). To calculate the ESS, a variance inflation factor V is first estimated for each block ([Wilks 2011](#), [Zwiers and Von Storch, 1995](#)) with:

$$V = 1 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right) r_k$$

Where n is the sample size and r is the autocorrelation at lag k . The ESS is then:

$$ESS = n / V$$

For large time series with more than 500 time points per block, a logarithmic lag sampling scheme is used to speed up calculation time.

Distribution Fit

Once the BMS has been constructed, a known statistical distribution can be fitted to model the distribution of extreme values. This distribution is then used to obtain the return values, periods, and probabilities.

The *climakitae* package offers the following probability distributions for modeling extreme values. While all of these distributions are frequently used in climate and hydrologic applications, the choice of distribution will depend on the specific application and underlying data ([Cooley 2011](#), [USGS 2019](#), [Katz 2002](#), [Furrer et al. 2010](#)). When in doubt, the [Generalized Extreme Value distribution](#) is a good starting point as it is commonly used with climate data and the BMS method ([Cooley 2009](#), [Coles 2001](#)).

- [Generalized extreme value \(GEV\) distribution](#)
- [Gumbel distribution](#)
- [Weibull distribution](#)
- [Generalized Pareto distribution](#)
- [Gamma distribution](#)
- [Pearson Type III distribution](#)

The [Kolmogorov-Smirnov \(K-S\) Goodness of Fit test](#) can be used to evaluate how well the selected probability distribution fits the data with the following null and alternative hypotheses ([Wilks 2011](#); for an example, see [Kharin 2007](#)):

- H_0 = input data is distributed according to the selected distribution
- H_1 = input data is not distributed according to the selected distribution

The corresponding p-value shows the significance of the fit:

- If p-value < α , reject H_0 . If p-value $\geq \alpha$, fail to reject H_0
- Where α is the significance level (often set to 0.05 or 5%)

The *climakitae* package can be used to obtain these p-values. Users should be aware that the K-S test is sensitive to sample size and p-values will change as sample size increases.

Once a distribution is selected, the [Maximum Likelihood Estimation](#) method is used to estimate the distribution parameters ([Coles 2001](#)). As currently implemented in *climakitae*, all parameters are constants.

The fitted probability distribution can then be used to calculate the return probability, return period, and return value as described below.

Return Probability

The [cumulative distribution function \(CDF\)](#) is calculated for the fitted probability distribution. Using the CDF, the exceedance probability is read for a desired return value ([Wilks 2011](#)). In the maximum case, the return probability is one minus the exceedance probability. In the minimum case, the return probability is equal to the exceedance probability.

- Maximum case: $\text{return_probability} = (1 - \text{fitted_distribution.cdf}(\text{return_value}))$
- Minimum case: $\text{return_probability} = \text{fitted_distribution.cdf}(\text{return_value})$

Figure 1 provides a demonstration of this procedure for the Maximum case.

Figure 1. This figure shows the CDF (right) for a GEV distribution (left) fitted to an AMS of daily maximum air temperature from a simulation. The return probability of 0.2 is read for a return value of 115°F (1 - 0.8

= 0.2), meaning that there is a 20% chance of temperatures exceeding 115°F in any given year at this location.

Return Period

The return probability is obtained as described above, then inverted to obtain the return period. Using the example in Figure 1, the return period would be $1 / 0.2$ or 5 years.

- $\text{return_period} = 1 / \text{return_probability}$

Return Value

A [percentage point function](#) (PPF, also known as an inverse CDF) ([Coles 2001](#)) for the fitted probability distribution is used to obtain the return value for a given event probability. In the maximum case, the event probability is one minus the return probability. In the minimum case, the event probability is equal to the return probability:

- Maximum case: $\text{return_value} = \text{fitted_distribution.ppf}(1 - \text{return_probability})$
- Minimum case: $\text{return_value} = \text{fitted_distribution.ppf}(\text{return_probability})$

Figure 2 provides a demonstration of this procedure for the Maximum case.

Figure 2. This figure shows the PPF for a GEV distribution fitted to an AMS of daily maximum air temperature from a simulation. The return value of 115°F is read for the return probability of 0.2 ($1 - 0.8 = 0.2$), meaning that there is a 20% chance of temperatures exceeding 115°F in any given year at this location.

Confidence Intervals

The bootstrap method is used to obtain confidence intervals on these return variables ([Efron and Tibshirani 1986](#), [Efron 1984](#)). This involves pulling random samples (with replacement) of the same sample size from the original BMS series and obtaining return variable estimates from those samples. *Climakitae* allows users to adjust the number of bootstrap samples, with 50–200 often being sufficient to obtain confidence limits ([Efron and Tibshirani 1986](#)). Percentiles are used to select the confidence limits from the bootstrapped estimates — for example, the 95% confidence intervals are obtained from the 2.5 and 97.5 percentile values of these estimates. These confidence intervals represent uncertainty due to internal variability and sampling error, but there are other sources of uncertainty in the return variable results such as model physics and scenario uncertainty that are not captured by these confidence intervals ([Kharin and Zwiers 2005](#)).

Aggregation

This section describes some general ways in which extreme value datasets can be aggregated. Users should always consider which methods are most appropriate for their specific applications.

Time Aggregation

Time aggregation may be used on input data as long as the final version of the input data is a time series. For example, an hourly precipitation time series could be resampled to a daily sum that is then used in the extreme value analysis.

Spatial Aggregation

Spatial aggregation can be applied prior to creating the BMS or after calculating extreme value results. For gridded data, *climakitae* threshold tools include an option to stack time series from multiple grid cells to increase sample size ([USGS 2019](#), [Katz 2002](#)). Alternatively, summary statistics such as spatial mean and median can be applied to a region to create a BMS for that entire region. Such statistics can also be applied to return variables, for example to obtain an average regional return value for a 1-in-10 event that has been calculated on a gridcell basis.

The stage at which spatial aggregation should be applied will depend on the variable used and research question being asked. For example, one investigation of basin-wide snow volume may require a single, basin-wide time series per simulation. A different investigation of extreme precipitation could focus on the most extreme return values in the region and choose to look at a spatial maximum of the return value. Users do not need to use any spatial aggregation and could instead look at single stations or maps of values.

Simulation Aggregation

When working with the [CMIP6](#) GCM data and tools provided on AE, extreme value analysis should be conducted on a simulation-by-simulation basis. Time series should not be aggregated over simulations, for example by taking a time mean by simulation, prior to creating the BMS. Each simulation should have its own time series and corresponding return variables.

Once the return variables are generated, it may be appropriate to aggregate by simulation. For example, a user interested in finding the return period of 105°F temperatures at a location could generate the return period by simulation and take the median over all the simulations. A subset of simulations could also be selected, such as simulations that have statistically significant p-values for the extreme value distribution fit.

There are many examples of multi-model assessments of return periods and return values in the peer-reviewed literature including [Kharin and Zwiers 2005](#), [Kharin 2007](#), and [Wehner et al. 2020](#).

Example Use Cases

Overview

The Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine (AE) is a web based climate data platform that analyzes historical and future conditions in context using the next generation of climate data. Through this work, the AE increases capacity for analysts and decision makers, especially in the energy sector, in preparing for extreme weather events, ongoing climate change, and understanding future warming conditions. The following are some methodologies to utilize the existing notebooks in practical application:

- Data Localization using the Getting Started Notebook
- Extreme Weather Events using the Threshold Exceedance Notebook
- Warming Levels using the Warming Levels Notebook

Data Localization

Understanding the changes to local climate supports decision making regarding asset management and ratepayer needs.

The Analytics Engine provides data localization capabilities to study and understand weather patterns at a local scale, by region, county, or city. Current energy forecasting methodologies rely on generalized data for a larger geographic area. With a dataset that covers a large geographic area, forecasting weather conditions for a specific location is difficult. The Python functions developed as part of AE provide paths to overcome that difficulty and understand specific projections.

For example, decision makers at a utility company traditionally use an existing model that produces electricity load forecasts based on historical weather observations. With Analytics Engine outputs, decision makers can now determine what *upcoming* climate conditions will affect load forecasting in a specific region. Functions within the Analytics Engine's [Interactive Data Access and Visualization notebook](#) demonstrate how to bias-correct gridded model observations at a weather station using the weather station's historical record and can guide users in:

- Identifying a time period and emission scenario
- Selecting weather station(s) in the location of interest
- Localizing gridded data to a weather station(s)
- Exporting for use outside of the Analytics Engine in an existing workflow

By using the time period, emissions scenario, and weather stations of interest AE can project air temperature and bias-correct the gridded model observations at that weather station. This notebook is fully customizable and offers visualizations of the data so that users can observe the overall pattern of and trends in bias-corrected air temperature within the AE models.

To learn more about the Analytics Engine's specific localization methodology, the [localization methodology notebook](#) walks through the quantile delta mapping (QDM) process of how the localized data is developed for a weather station. This notebook provides step by step instructions on the localization process within the Select tool of the Getting Started notebook.

Extreme Weather Events

Exploring the extremes in temperature allows for the prioritization of temperature mitigation resources for both extreme heat and extreme cold.

The Analytics Engine provides the [Threshold Exceedance notebook](#) to identify the number of events that would surpass a threshold (e.g. 115° F) to proactively make decisions regarding asset management, including mitigation, maintenance, and design upgrades. For example, with the Threshold Exceedance notebook, an engineer could reliably estimate the number of extreme heat events in air temperature for a specific location to better prioritize equipment design and future siting of asset locations.

Within the Threshold Exceedance notebook, a user can:

- Select a geographic area and time period of interest
- Select a variable of interest (e.g., air temperature, precipitation)
- Define the extreme event (threshold, recurrence interval, and duration of event*). The event exceedance plot thus illustrates the projected frequency of extreme events at the selected threshold and duration and can also be used in additional models or analysis.

Warming Levels

An approach to separate timing from the impacts to climate and make dynamic plans based on the amount of warming in the world.

The Analytics Engine's [Warming Levels notebook](#) provides detail on the regional response to a given level of global warming, and illustrates how to overlay user data to help identify vulnerable locations. As an example, the Warming Levels notebook looks at power plants in connection to the regional response at a specific warming level. With the Warming Levels notebook, users are able to:

- Visualize and compare the differences in the regional response across models at four different warming levels (1.5°, 2°, 3°, and 4°C of warming)
- Export data at a warming level across models for specific application needs

In the Warming Levels notebook, a user would first select a geographic region and warming level to analyze the range of responses across the different models. Users would then be able to visualize the change in the selected climate variable from the historical climate at the designated warming level, with options to see different warming levels. In other words, it would show how much warmer, with temperature selected, a specific county would be when the world is 2° warmer.

With this information, a city planner could identify the local impacts of a warming trajectory and build plans to support the needs of that community at that warming level. Understanding warming levels at the regional scale can help inform regional policy decisions. For example, if more precipitation occurs at a certain warming level, policies around stormwater or flooding response can be planned and implemented in preparation of reaching that warming level.

It's very important to be able to build plans for the scenarios (i.e., a specific warming level) and not the time (i.e., 50 years from now) because the timing of various climate impacts is highly variable due to model uncertainty and human actions, and ultimately focus on preparing for a likely scenario regardless of timing.
